

Maintaining Space With The Help of 3D Printing - A Case Report

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Abstract

Preventive orthodontics in pediatric dentistry, involves a unique set of skills and knowledge aimed at ensuring proper tooth alignment in growing children. One of the most reliable methods to prevent future malocclusions due to premature tooth loss is the placement of a space maintainer (SM), which helps preserve the space until the corresponding permanent tooth erupts. Traditionally, the fabrication of SMs has been a meticulous and time-intensive process, requiring close coordination with dental laboratories to ensure precise fit and function. Advances in digital technology, particularly the use of three-dimensional (3D) printing, have streamlined this process by minimizing manual errors and enhancing fabrication efficiency. This paper explores the integration of digital methods in pediatric dentistry for the development of innovative SM designs and presents a related clinical case.

Keywords : 3D printing, digital scanner, CAD-CAM, Micro laser sintering, 3D printed space maintainer

Introduction

Dental caries remains a significant public health issue, often resulting in the premature loss or extraction of affected teeth^[1]. Early loss of primary teeth can interfere with the natural eruption of permanent teeth, leading to complications such as malocclusion and discrepancies in arch length^[2]. Consequently, it becomes critical to preserve the space left by prematurely lost primary teeth to prevent problems like crowding, ectopic eruptions, unopposed tooth supra-eruption, and midline shifts^[3].

According to the American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry (AAPD), space maintenance involves retaining the current alignment of teeth to prevent the loss of dental arch dimensions, including length, width, and perimeter^[4]. The term “space maintenance” was introduced in 1941 by JC Brauer, who described it as the method of maintaining oral space left vacant by the loss of one or more teeth^[5]. Space maintainers are devices designed to prevent the neighbouring teeth from shifting into the gap, ensuring enough room for the permanent teeth to erupt properly. These appliances can be either fixed or removable, used on one (unilateral) or both (bilateral) sides of the dental arch, and may

be functional (supporting chewing) or non-functional.

Although conventional space maintainers have been widely used in pediatric dentistry, they present several limitations. These include subpar construction, time-intensive and costly lab work, potential processing errors, and difficulties in obtaining dental impressions, especially in young children who may have a strong gag reflex. These issues have prompted the development of alternative space maintainers, such as fiber-reinforced composite and prefabricated designs, which offer quicker fabrication and enhanced patient comfort. However, they too can encounter challenges like debonding at the enamel-composite and fiber-composite junctions, as well as issues related to polymerization shrinkage^[5].

Modern dentistry has increasingly turned to digital workflows in fabricating space maintainers, offering numerous advantages over traditional methods. Technological innovations introduced during the 1990s and

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early 2000s revolutionized dental practices^[6]. One such advancement is 3D printing, a process that constructs objects layer by layer based on digital models. The digital blueprint is broken into thin slices, which are sequentially built by the printer. Digital scanners capture the anatomical details needed for designing these models, which are then saved in STL (standard tessellation language) file format and sent to the labs where CAD-CAM technology is used for designing the appliance and then transferred to the printer for its fabrication^[7].

Case History

A 7-year-old male presented to the Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry with a complaint of a missing teeth in the lower right posterior region, persisting for the past 10 days. The patient reported pain in the region 15 days prior and was taken to a general dentist, who extracted the primary first and second molar (tooth 84, 85) (Figure-1). An intraoral periapical radiograph (IOPA) taken in the region of tooth^{84,85} showed the underlying premolar in Nolla's developmental stage 4, indicating an early stage of tooth development^[8]. Both arches were scanned using 3 Shape TRIOS 3 scanner (3 Shape, Denmark) (Figure-2 and 3). The scanned file was saved in STL (standard tessellation language) format and was sent to the laboratory, where 3D model was designed. The appliance was designed using CAD-CAM software^[9] and was fabricated using micro laser sintering, an additive manufacturing process using a titanium alloy powder (Ti64 Gd23) from LPW Technology Ltd., UK. This method enables precise fabrication and superior material properties suitable for intraoral use^[10,11]. The space maintainer was trial-fitted, showing accurate adaptation. It was cemented using Type 2 Glass Ionomer Cement (GC Fuji, Tokyo, Japan) (Figure-4), known for its good biocompatibility and fluoride release^[12].

The patient was advised to avoid food and drink for 30 minutes post-cementation and to avoid chewing hard food using the appliance side. A follow-up appointment was scheduled after six months to evaluate appliance integrity and observe the eruptive progress of the premolar. (Figure-5)

Figure - 2

Figure - 3

Figure - 4

Figure - 1

Figure - 5

Discussion

Loss of space in the primary and mixed dentition is a common clinical occurrence. Early intervention plays a critical role in reducing the need for extensive orthodontic treatment later in life by preserving the dental arch integrity^[13]. Space loss may occur due to various reasons such as trauma, idiopathic conditions, or premature extractions of primary teeth^[2].

The conventional Band and Loop space maintainer is one of the most widely used fixed appliances, especially for single missing teeth^[14]. Despite its widespread use, the conventional Band and Loop appliance has certain limitations, including: The need for physical impressions and cast pouring, Multiple-step laboratory fabrication, Risk of decementation and solder joint failures and Multiple patient visits for delivery and adjustments^[15].

This has highlighted the demand for advanced materials and design techniques in space maintenance^[16]. One such innovation is 3D printing, which allows the creation of solid, physical dental appliances directly from digital designs. This technique eliminates the need for conventional impression-taking, casting, and soldering, significantly reducing chairside time and laboratory effort^[17]. Using intraoral scanners (e.g., 3Shape TRIOS 3 scanner) and CAD software (such as DentalCAD by Exocad), dental professionals can design precise space maintainers digitally. These are then fabricated as a single, seamless unit using materials like titanium or biocompatible resins, enhancing durability and reducing chances of failure^[18].

3D printed space maintainers have demonstrated several clinical advantages like enhanced precision and fit, reducing appliance failure, smoother surface finish, lowering plaque accumulation and gingival inflammation. It offers improved patient and parent satisfaction due to comfort and reduced visits and elimination of solder joints, decreasing long-term maintenance needs^[19]. Although initial setup of digital dentistry equipment can be costly and requires staff training, the long-term benefits in terms of accuracy, efficiency, and patient compliance justify the investment^[20].

Conclusion

The presented 3D Printed space maintainer is found to be precise, quick and child friendly.

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